

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

JEALOUSY AS PSYCHOEMOTIONAL TRAUMA

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Abstract

The present study has focused on the dimension of jealousy existing in different age groups. The results indicate that participants of younger age have a statistically significant lower level of jealousy compared to the other two age groups: 25–29 and 30–35. An explanation would be that the group of participants from the group category 18–24 years ($N = 60$) are less involved in and assumed towards romantic relationships, more important for them being socialization and the group of friends, especially during the period of after Covid 19, when these aspects were considerably absent from their lives.

Keywords: psychoemotional trauma, jealousy, couple partner, neuroscience.

Introduction

Psychoemotional trauma represents the effect left by emotional disorders which manifest mostly due to unmet emotional needs and can be displayed throughout adulthood.

Generally speaking, trauma has been called “the hidden epidemic” since various aspects of individual’s personality development (such as social encounters, friendships, romantic relationships, socializing needs) can be affected by it. Life experience inside dysfunctional families might lead to psychoemotional trauma which in its turn can become trans-generational determining as such the decision one takes in relationship while choosing their partner.

When jealousy, as a negative emotion, emerges in a relationship it should be seen as a dysfunctional attitude bearing the shape of an attachment trauma. We tend to choose our partner according to our own needs, be they conscious or unconscious, and our mental programs that have been deeply implanted in our subconscious by early childhood connections to our parents. As a result one may find out that he got married to figure similar to his mother or she got married to figure resembling her father. It is an aspect that one becomes aware long after they get married.

The choice of a partner should come from that ground of fulfillment, but unfortunately there is no educational culture and no psychoeducation to teach us that. Thus we end up choosing relationships that can meet our unfulfilled needs of a specific developmental stage.

At 16 of age, there is the need to spend more time with our partner, given the fact that teenagers at this stage still live with their parents. This tends to be the main language of love.

At 20 of age we are drawn towards a career path and we enroll in a college and at the same time we want for our partner to join us if at all possible.

At 30 we start talking about different principles and values and it becomes pretty clear that at some time in life we have specific needs that start changing as the time passes by and we grow older.

For a woman, in search of a partner in a relationship, she will look for the man of her dreams who is always there to provide for her needs: the need for se-

curity, for tenderness, the need to be supported and contained – the natural needs. According to Roberto Assagioli, renown psychiatrist and the father of psychosynthesis, we, as human beings, have a multitude of subpersonalities. He elaborated a validly sustained theory according to which subpersonalities make up the general portrait of our personality.

One such subpersonality encompasses an entire set of needs, beliefs and ways of behaving helping us to interact with another person. For instance, I hold the role of mother when I am with my child, while I hold the position of a manager when I am at my working place.

Therefore it appears to be very important to consider from which subpersonality I decide to choose my wife or my husband, since each of these subpersonalities has its own core of specific needs. For instance, if I am more in the role of a little girl, I will choose a partner to fulfill the role of a father for that girl. In order to identify this potential partner, it is important to ask one what are one’s needs, *e.g.* is it there a financial need, is there the need to have someone to rely on when I want to pick up a travel destination etc. The way I see myself in relation to him will not be from the equal positions, but mostly from that of a daughter-father positions. This type of marriage won’t be for the long run, that’s for sure.

When going for a date we usually have some expectations from the person we are about to meet. For instance, a man expects the woman to tell him what sort of a shirt he is supposed to wear; later on, maybe, to decide on his behalf what color should his furniture have; in short, to control him. On the other hand, the woman expects her partner on a first date to tell her what job is good for her, how to wear her make-up in the morning, how to make a choice – all these come not from the role of a partner, but rather from a position of authority that she invested him with, becoming as such, dependent on his moods and states of mind. Once this happens, nobody can be happy about it, because the person will turn into the child in search of a parent. It is the need to continue having the relationship with their parents or, in the situation of a childhood trauma, to replace it.

Whenever we are looking for something, there must be something that we are missing. When we talk

about a fulfilled romantic relationship, this one should have its start from a plus position – if I am fulfilled I can start looking for a partner who could sustain me with continuing fulfillment. Whereas if I am on a minus position and I expect that someone else would meet my needs, then I already start from a wrong position within a romantic relationship. I will become dependent on the other person's states of mind. If both of us had been independent, then we would live a life at its extremes.

It is therefore important to find a co-dependency in relationship where we could ask the right questions to identify our partner. In his book, "*I am OK – You are OK*", Thomas Harris promotes the idea that if a partner is not OK, having big expectations from their partner, then they won't perceive the other as being OK either. On the other hand, being self-fulfilled, having a good emotional and overall mental balance, one will be able to offer their love and choose their partner from a plus position.

Choosing a partner for the sake of having someone to support myself, to have something to offer, it means that subconsciously I choose from a position of lacking something. But when I, as a woman, bring in my feminine energy, my availability, gentleness and power to contain you, then it is a totally different position. When a man brings into the relationship his own emotional stability, his common sense, understanding the emotional flow of each and every mood triggered by the inevitable daily stress, then he can be a good candidate for a partner who is committed to the relationship.

But as long as I am not satisfied as a person, then I can't see the other one as a good match, on contrary, this thing can lead to anxiety. I will inevitably relate to the reptilian brain and at my first date I will be tempted to pick up on the smallest detail of my partner's behavior, telling myself that he is not paying enough attention to my needs.

We all need to be respected, to be heard, to be mirrored when we talk to each other. Being on a date doesn't imply only a physical encounter, but also an interaction with somebody else's soul, with their own values. It is an interaction that evolves on different levels. The encounter is the first one, followed by the stage of getting to know the other.

If from the very start you feel ignored or used in some way, if your partner pays more attention to their phone or to their own needs, without acknowledging you, it shows immaturity on their behalf. This means that they are not there to meet you, to greet you, to get to know you. It is therefore very important to adjust our expectations in accordance to the moment that we together, as a couple, are creating. Beyond respect, there is the need for attention and the need to spend time together without skipping the specific stages of a date, creating space for the other to exist, while making a difference between extreme expectations and tolerable humanity. Holding a mutual esteem for each other's identity, getting to know certain attitudes, rules, good manners - these are some of the aspects that allow women to preserve their feminine energy and men to step into their own masculinity offering as such the possibility for a second date.

Showing interest in the other partner involves giving the other some space for expressing themselves, for asking questions, mirroring the other at the level of "I am here because I want to get to know you at every aspect of yourself". It is therefore recommended to draw beforehand a 'sketch' of what exactly it is we want to bring in a lasting relationship, what exactly it is that we need to co-create together with our partner. Having this sort of clarity, will enable us to make room for different aspects (like: different interests, passions, and not being "the twin-partner") owned by each partner, while he gets to preserve his psychoemotional masculinity and she preserving her own psychoemotional femininity.

As human beings we are a work in progress and knowing our own needs and features from previous unfulfilled relationships will become benchmarks for our future relationships. For instance, a childhood fraught with adversities will turn adulthood into a life fraught with neuroticism, according to Jeronimus & al. (2013). The child's brain develops in stages that are shaped by the environmental needs that help him survive.

In literature (Siegel, 2011, Cozolino, 2014) we find that attachment trauma leads to certain behaviors, therefore it is important to know the neural mechanisms involved in this process. Alongside with this, the level of development into emotional intelligence is a must-know when it comes to interacting with others.

At birth, neurons located in the limbic system (which is the brain area for emotional learning - the basis into establishing the subjective sense of self and of others) are not completely developed. Genetically speaking, these neurons are "wired" to form synaptic connections through relational experiences that one has with those close to them. Through mutual interactions and emotional availability of the care providers, these brain regions will be activated and start their growth process, including the release of connectivity and pleasure hormones through intimate and contingent relating.

Any type of experience will result in wiring brain neurons and once this action is repeated, the same neurons will fire together, connecting each other into reinforced neuronal pathways. These ones will end up becoming reaction patterns (including here attachment patterns) and the entire brain structure will mature in the same way.

Neuroscience can explain the neural mechanisms involved in attachment trauma, according to recent researches [1]. Amygdala is the center of fear and represents the basis of emotional learning due to socializing, but it maintains also a big role in storing the experimented reactions.

Hippocampus, attached to the limbic system, is responsible with storing memories both at subconscious and conscious level. Hypothalamus is in charge with releasing the hormones, the most important one being oxytocin – the hormone of affective connection released together with the touch, warmth contained for instance, in breast feeding of a baby. This is the reason why we feel connected and safe every time the loved ones hug us or we remember people who offered us unconditional love.

Healing attachment trauma is a process that requires acknowledging one's coping strategies they developed to help them deal with intense situations. These strategies come in the form of defenses that block the emotions, resulting in a behavior that is meant to avoid the painful stimulus or to confront it in a dysfunctional manner.

Neuroplasticity is the new term in psychology literature which indicates that viewing things through a new perspective, a new filter, we could understand better the other person while using the familiar past so that we won't have to make the same choices. This entails practicing awareness, creating a positive mindset, defining and developing a new subpersonality, that of a lover.

We often tend to make choices based on trauma experience and our life script and so it happens that our partner who could be quite suitable, albeit different, might end up appearing kind of boring to us.

However, things do not evolve so quickly, they take their normal, quite path starting with a friendship that doesn't necessarily exclude the erotic attraction between the partners. In fact, the state of 'being in love' is not similar to that of having found the desired one; we must not exclude those moments of dating where there are no fireworks, no dramas, no fights; those moments where we are not carried into the limbic brain activating the sympathetic nervous system. If not, all these could mean that we choose from our trauma history, searching for that intensity which is often poisonous and turning our relationships into toxic ones.

From a psychotherapy perspective, we can easily get trapped into the dynamic called Drama Triangle (according to Stephen Karpman who developed the concept). It is overwhelming for a man to become the Rescuer for the little girl inside his partner. He turns into her bank cards provider, holiday maker, anything she wishes and needs for. This part of his, generates a Victim position in his partner, a position that she is not aware of, but at the same time comes with all sorts of restrictions.

Other times, women turn into a trophy-partner and this is where the Persecutor comes in. She can be quite aggressive or he is the passive-aggressor not offering what she desires for. Her answer, in turn, would be punishment since she knows very well that she is his trophy to boast about to the world. All these types of relationships are profoundly transactional.

Long term relationships come in the form of "intentional dating" which reflects the way we feel around that partner, whether or not we share the same values, paying attention to the rhythm of living the other one prefers, how much freedom we get from that relationship.

Traditionally speaking, we develop in several stages: first we are children, who get bored with the same toys, then we become teenagers with growth hormones to increase the level of irritability, playing havoc around us. That doesn't mean that once teenage years are over, we stop being teenagers. On contrary, we tend to be the same teenagers as adults giving up a relationship and rapidly choosing a new partner. This is a sure way to avoid the commitment that maturity comes with.

Being superficial, irritable, pretentious is the way to be for that stage of life where psychoemotional development is at its beginning. It's important to own one's commitment, but first of all towards ourselves and this can happen through the power of communication. Talking to people of opposite sex leads to another stage wherein we select and get to know ourselves through different relationships. For a teenage female-partner it is the right start to crystallize into the future woman. Now it is not the time to behave as if she is already married or goes by the marriage rules. The relationship becomes her space where she defines herself as a woman.

Having an efficient and committed communication implies that at least one of the partners to become involved in an open discussion. Those who steer away from commitment are in different stages of development and have different needs; it all comes down to emotional maturity.

It is important to understand that if you are not chosen as a partner or as a friend, it is not about you, but rather about the other person's taste.

Physical attraction seems to be, at least at the beginning, very important because one shares their emotional intimacy with another. Erotic and sexual intimacies seem to come at later time, since emotional intimacy lays the foundation for sexuality.

Emotional compatibility persists throughout time, even long after hormonal period and consists of being open and courageous enough to show yourself the way you truly are.

Once we become aware of ourselves, we can identify the patterns according to which we tend to make our choices. These choices go hand in hand with our present behavior and our developmental needs. Once we step out of our subconscious archetypal patterns we will be able to choose freely.

Trauma can be the consequence of an experience loaded with suffering or of recurrent events that have been too overwhelming to bear, events that have lasted for weeks or even years, throughout which the individual has struggled to adjust, but in the end suffering seriously negative results, such as: anxiety, major depression, substance or/and alcohol abuse.

Researches indicate the relationship between jealousy and alcohol abuse with the following conclusions:

- alcoholism plays an etiological role in developing morbid jealousy [7]

- in men, there is a negative correlation between sexual jealousy and sexual satisfaction and conjugal stability; in women there is a negative correlation between sexual jealousy and marriage duration and a positive correlation with severity of alcohol addiction [9]

- pathological jealousy is wide spread in both men and women, more so with old age.

The antecedents of this affliction can be of neurological nature or related to drugs or even psychological, more often preceded by low self esteem and excessive dependency to the romantic partner. Pathological jealousy can be triggered by the partner's behavior and maintained by errors in judgment and by psychological benefits that are initially rendered to the relationship itself [8].

The present research has aimed into identifying the relationships between personality traits and various intra- and inter-personal factors regarding the dysfunctional jealous behavior. The sample consisting of 180 participants (aged between 18 and 35) has been investigated to find out the relationship between age and level of jealousy.

We took into account the observations and interviews performed in prior couple therapy sessions as well as individual sessions.

According to the results, it appears that the jealousy level ($m=13.92$) in the younger age group (18 – 24 yo) seems to be lower when compared to the jealousy level ($m=17.8$) of older individuals (25 – 29 yo) and those of 30 – 35 yo ($m=17.58$). (Table 1)

Table 1

Descriptive statistics of participants on age groups according to jealousy as dependent variable

Age group	DV	N	Min	Max	Median	Mean	SD
18-24	jealousy	60	12.00	19.00	13.00	13.92	1.66
25-29	jealousy	60	16.00	20.00	18.00	17.80	1.34
30-35	jealousy	60	16.00	20.00	18.00	17.58	1.39

Comparing other findings in literature which indicate that with aging the jealousy level tends to decrease [5] and jealousy is at its peak during teenage years [6], the results of our study indicate the contrary: participants in younger group have a statistically significant lower level of jealousy when compared to the other age groups: 25-29 and 30- 35 ($Wilcoxon(60, 60)=169.5$, $p < 0.001$, $es= 0.79$), ($Wilcoxon(60, 60)=205$, $p < 0.001$, $es= 0.77$). This can be explained by the fact that participants in first group (18-24, $N = 60$) could be less involved and less committed to romantic relationships, more important for them being socializing and group of peers, especially following the Covid-19 times, when these things have been absent from their life. Additionally, youngsters in Romania, at this group of age are more in search of exploring their identity, emphasizing other aspects of their life, such as enrolling in the right college, looking for a job to provide the least comfort for their life, while romantic relationships become just a detail in their need for socializing. But with aging, individuals tend to become more aware of what entails being involved in a romantic relationship and it is possible that the pressure of such a responsibility to implicitly activate their unresolved attachment traumas.

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